

1
2
3 1 **A new mutualism between *Chlamydomonas* and *Methylobacteria* facilitates growth**
4 **on amino acids and peptides**
5
6

7
8 4 Victoria Calatrava¹, Erik F. Y. Hom², Ángel Llamas¹, Emilio Fernández¹, Aurora
9 Galván^{1,*}, †
10

11
12
13 7 ¹Dpto. de Bioquímica y Biología Molecular. Campus de Rabanales y Campus
14 Internacional de Excelencia Agroalimentario (CeIA3). Edif. Severo Ochoa, Universidad
15 de Córdoba, Spain.
16

17
18 | ² Department of Biology, University of Mississippi, University MS 38677, USA
19

20
21
22 *Corresponding author, E-mail: bb1gacea@uco.es

23 †Aurora Galvan, orcid.org/0000-0002-7564-2281
24

25
26 15 **One sentence summary:** A carbon-nitrogen exchange based mutualism between the
27 alga *Chlamydomonas* and *Methylobacterium spp.* improves the growth of both cell
28 types on amino acids and peptides
29
30

31
32
33 19 **Editors:** María Dolores Roldán and David J Richardson
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

23 **ABSTRACT**

24 Nitrogen is a key nutrient for land plants and phytoplankton in terrestrial and aquatic
25 ecosystems. The model alga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* can use and grow efficiently
26 on several inorganic nitrogen sources (e.g., ammonium, nitrate, nitrite) as well as many
27 amino acids. In this study, we show that *Chlamydomonas* is unable to use proline,
28 hydroxyproline, and peptides that contain these amino acids. However, we discovered
29 that algal growth on these substrates is supported in association with *Methylobacterium*
30 *spp.*, and that a mutualistic carbon-nitrogen metabolic exchange between
31 *Chlamydomonas* and *Methylobacterium spp* is established. Specifically, the
32 mineralization of these amino acids and peptides by *Methylobacterium spp* produces
33 ammonium that can be assimilated by *Chlamydomonas*, and CO₂ photosynthetically
34 fixed by *Chlamydomonas* yields glycerol that can be assimilated by *Methylobacterium*.
35 As *Chlamydomonas* is an algal ancestor to land plants and *Methylobacterium* is a plant
36 growth-promoting bacterium (PGPB), this new model mutualism may facilitate insights
37 into the ecology and evolution of plant-bacterial interactions and design principles of
38 synthetic ecology.

39

40 **Keywords:** Algal-bacterial mutualism, *Chlamydomonas*, *Methylobacterium*, metabolic
41 complementation, nitrogen assimilation

42

43 INTRODUCTION

44 Nitrogen (N) is one of the major limiting nutrients for primary producers like plants and
45 phytoplankton in terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Although elemental N is abundant,
46 it is often not bioavailable for most organisms. Plants and phytoplankton depend on the
47 abilities of other microorganisms to transform inaccessible N sources into assimilable
48 forms like ammonium and nitrate (Hirsch and Mauchline 2015; Pajares and Bohannan
49 2016). Often, these ecological dependencies evolve and yield stable interactions
50 between organisms with improved efficiency in nutrient exchange. A well-known
51 example is the formation of nodules by N-fixing bacteria in plant roots, which provides
52 an excellent environment in which N₂ from the air can be efficiently transformed into
53 assimilable N for plants. This symbiosis has allowed plants to thrive in N-limiting
54 environments. In contexts where inorganic N is limiting but organic N is present,
55 microorganisms can play a fundamental role in mineralizing N into bioavailable forms
56 for photosynthetic organisms. Such microbes include plant growth-promoting bacteria
57 (PGPB), which have been well studied because of their positive influence on plant
58 fitness (for a review, see de Souza *et al.* 2015). Such mutualistic bacterial interactions
59 are not only limited to land plants, but also extend to the green algae (Xie *et al.* 2013;
60 Hom *et al.* 2015; Tanabe *et al.* 2015) The dominant bacterial species within the plant
61 rhizosphere are mostly shared with those found in the planktonic analogue or
62 ‘phycosphere’, suggesting that algal-bacterial associations might have coevolved
63 (Goecke *et al.* 2013; Kim *et al.* 2014; Ramanan *et al.* 2015a,b; Seymour *et al.* 2017).
64 Furthermore, the ability of bacteria to benefit algae has been a recently exploited
65 strategy to advance biotechnological applications (Wu *et al.* 2012; Li *et al.* 2013; Wirth
66 *et al.* 2015; Cho *et al.* 2015; Mahdavi *et al.* 2015). A better understanding of such
67 interactions will not only cast light on the evolutionary and ecological aspects of plant-
68 microbe associations, but will have practical ramifications for the biotechnological
69 industry. The use of model organisms towards this end could be particularly effective
70 given their experimental tractability.

71 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* (*Chlamydomonas*) has been a powerful model
72 system for studying N metabolism in algae and plants (Galván and Fernández 2007;
73 Sanz-Luque *et al.* 2015). Although *Chlamydomonas* preferentially uses inorganic N (i.e.
74 ammonium, nitrate and nitrite), it can use some organic N sources such as amino acids
75 and purines, albeit with significantly lower efficiency (Kirk and Kirk 1978). For
76 *Chlamydomonas*, assimilation of N from amino acids occurs via a periplasmic L-amino

1
2
3 77 acid oxidase (CrLAO1) that deaminates amino acids to generate α keto-acid and
4 78 ammonium, which is then efficiently assimilated. Some amino acids such as L-Pro and
5 79 L-Hyp are not deaminated by CrLAO1 (Vallon *et al.* 1993), however, and very little is
6 80 known about the ability of *Chlamydomonas* to grow on peptides as a sole N source. To
7 81 date, only high-throughput screening results based on cellular respiration reactions of
8 82 *Chlamydomonas* grown on a few di- and tripeptides have been published
9 83 (Chaiboonchoe *et al.* 2014). However, it is unclear from this study how or whether
10 84 *Chlamydomonas* is able to grow on peptides as sole N sources. In this work, we
11 85 demonstrate the inability of *Chlamydomonas* to grow on certain amino acids or peptides
12 86 as a sole N source and show how this inability can be complemented by PGPB
13 87 *Methylobacterium* species in co-culture.

14
15
16 88 Methylobacteria are pink-pigmented, facultative methylotrophs (PPFM) that are
17 89 found on the surface of most plant species where they grow using the methanol released
18 90 by plant stomas as a byproduct of cell-wall degradation during plant cell growth
19 91 (Abanda-Nkpwatt *et al.* 2006). PPFMs have been extensively reported to benefit plant
20 92 hosts by fixing atmospheric nitrogen or by inhibiting plant-pathogens (Sy *et al.* 2001;
21 93 Madhaiyan *et al.* 2006). Evidence suggests that *Methylobacterium* species may have co-
22 94 evolved as photosymbionts of bryophytes, which are ancestral to land plants (Kutschera
23 95 2007). Here, we describe a new interaction between *Chlamydomonas* and
24 96 *Methylobacterium* that could provide key insights into the evolution of plant-PPFM
25 97 interactions and serve as a new model system for studies in synthetic ecology that may
26 98 be of biotechnological relevance.

27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41 99
42 100
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

101 MATERIALS AND METHODS

102 Strains, culture media and pre-culture conditions

103 Wild-type CC-1690 (Sager 21 gr) *Chlamydomonas* cells were pre-cultured in Tris-
104 Acetate-Phosphate (TAP) medium (Gormant and Levine 1965) containing 8 mM of
105 ammonium chloride, for 2-3 days (exponential growth phase) at 25 °C under continuous
106 light and agitation.

107 *Methylobacterium* strains (summarized in Table 1) were pre-cultured in a
108 modified CYB minimal salts medium (Hom and Murray (2014)) that we refer to as
109 MeM (*Methylobacterium* Medium), for which potassium nitrate (1g/L), peptone (2.5
110 g/L) and methanol (0.5%) are added. Pre-cultures were grown for 2-3 days at 25 °C and
111 agitation to ensure that cells were in exponential growth.

112 Potential culture contamination was routinely checked by streaking each liquid
113 pre-culture on modified TAP-gellan gum (1.7%) plates supplemented with tryptone (2.5
114 g/L) for *Chlamydomonas* cultures or on MeM-gellan gum (1.7%) plates for
115 *Methylobacterium* cultures, incubated for 2 weeks at 25°C, and examined under a
116 microscope.

118 Growth on amino acids and peptides

119 Mono- and coculture experiments were performed in CYB medium with the indicated
120 L-amino acid or peptide (8 mM) as sole N and/or C source. All L-amino acids and
121 peptides were dissolved in CYB and filter-sterilized (0.2 µm). Prior to filtering, pH was
122 adjusted as needed to 7.2 ± 0.1 using KOH or HCl.

123 *Chlamydomonas* and *Methylobacterium* pre-cultures in exponential growth were
124 each harvested by centrifugation for 2-3 min at 3,000 rpm, washed three times using
125 CYB and used independently (monocultures) or in combination (co-culture) to achieve
126 a final A_{750} of 0.025 for algal and A_{600} of 0.002 for bacterial cultures in a final volume
127 of 250 µl in sterile V-bottom 96-wells culture plates (BRANDplates®) These culutres
128 were incubated at 25 °C under continuous light, and after 8-12 days, cells cultures in the
129 plates were pelleted by centrifugation (5 min, 3,000 rpm) for imaging from below.

130 All growth experiments were performed at least twice including two biological
131 replicates per experiment.

132

133 Identification of methylobacterial contamination

134 *Methylobacterium* contamination was isolated by plate streaking a *Chlamydomonas*

1
2
3 135 culture growing on L-Ala-Ala to generate single colonies and identified by colony PCR
4 136 amplification and subsequent amplicon sequencing of the highly conserved UARR
5 137 region of 16S rDNA as described by (Rivas *et al.* 2004) using primers U1F (5'-CTY
6 138 AAA KRA ATT GRC GGR RRS SC-3') and U1R (5'-CGG GCG GTG TGT RCA
7 139 ARR SSC-3'). (Accession number sent to NCBI)

140 | **Coculture growth quantification by qPCR**

141 To simultaneously quantify *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* and *Methylobacterium*
142 *aquaticum* growth, species-specific primers were designed using Primer3
143 (<http://primer3.ut.ee/>) and BLAST to amplify single-copy genes. To quantify algal
144 growth, 213 bp of the *Chlamydomonas centrin* gene (Cre11.g468450.t1.2) were
145 amplified using primers Cen1CreU (5'-TTA CAA GAT GGG ACA GCC CG-3') and
146 Cen1CreL (5'-CAG CCC GCA GAG GAA CTA AC-3'). To quantify bacterial growth,
147 239 bp of *rpoB* gene (Maq22A_c27070) were amplified using primers rpoBMaqU (5'-
148 TAG ATG TAG CCG ACC GTG AC-3') and rpoBMaqL (5'- ATG AAG GCG ATC
149 TAC AGC GA-3'). To generate the calibration curves, each PCR product of the two
150 above-mentioned gene fragments were cloned into pSpark® I vector (Canvax Biotech
151 S.L.) and used to transform *Escherichia coli* DH5 α . Individual clones were selected and
152 confirmed by DNA sequencing. The corresponding pDNA was quantified and 3 μ l-
153 aliquots (containing 10¹⁰ copies/ μ l) were stored at -20°C on TE buffer. For each qPCR
154 run, 1 μ l of each standard aliquot (*centrin* and *rpoB*) was serially 10-fold diluted, from
155 10⁹ to 10¹ copies, and loaded in the same qPCR plate to quantify gene copies. qPCR
156 was performed using SsoFast EvaGreen Supermix (Bio-Rad), and run and detected in
157 MyiQ™2 (Bio-Rad) detection system. The conditions used for qPCR were: initial
158 denaturation at 98°C for 2 min and 40 cycles of 5 s of denaturation at 98°C and 10 s of
159 annealing and extension at 61°C. One ml of sample was used to extract gDNA using a
160 standard phenol-chloroform extraction protocol (Sambrook *et al.* 1989).

161 To validate cell number quantification by qPCR, gDNA of serially diluted *C.*
162 *reinhartii* and *M. aquaticum* cultures were isolated and used for single-copy gene
163 quantification by qPCR. Each of the serially diluted cell cultures were also plated to
164 quantify CFUs to confirm results obtained by qPCR. CFU and qPCR quantifications of
165 three biological replicates of three different dilutions of cell cultures resulted in a r^2
166 value of 0.992 for *C. reinhardtii* and 0.993 for *M. aquaticum* cultures.

167

1
2
3 168 **Metabolite quantification**

4 169 Ammonium concentrations in the culture supernatants was determined by the use of
5
6 170 Nessler reagent (Koch and McMeekin 1924). A Nessler reagent mixture was prepared
7
8 171 by mixing equal volumes of Nessler reagents A and B (MERCK 109011 and 109012,
9
10 172 respectively). 1 ml of bacterial cultures were harvested by centrifugation and 100 µl-
11
12 173 samples of cell-free supernatants were transferred to flat-bottom 96-wells microtiter
13
14 174 plates. 100 µl of freshly prepared Nessler reagent mixture was added, incubated for 2
15
16 175 min and A₄₁₀ was read using a microplate reader (iMark™, Bio-Rad). Ammonium
17
18 176 calibration curves were included in every measurement and samples were diluted as
19
20 177 needed.

21 178 Glycerol accumulation in the medium was analyzed by HPLC (Agilent series
22 179 1200, Agilent Technologies Spain) using a previously established protocol (Jurado-
23 180 Oller *et al.* 2015) involving isocratic elution of sulphuric acid (5 mM) at 55°C in an ion-
24 181 exchange column (Agilent Hi-Plex H, 300 x 7.7 mm, 6 µm I.D.). 100 µl of culture
25 182 supernatants recovered after centrifugation were filtered (0.2 µm) and analyzed by
26 183 HPLC using RID (Refractive Index Detector, Agilent G 1362A, Agilent Technologies).
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

186 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

187

188 ***Methylobacterium* complements the inability of *Chlamydomonas* to grow using**
189 **peptides**

190 We analysed *Chlamydomonas* growth on a number of dipeptides under axenic
191 conditions that led to a typical N-starved phenotype and were not able to grow. In the
192 course of experimentation, we observed an unexpected ‘pink’ contamination of a L-Ala-
193 Ala culture that enabled *Chlamydomonas* to grow efficiently. We proceeded to isolate
194 this contaminant through repeated colony re-streaking and sequenced PCR-amplified
195 product of the conserved UARR region of 16S rDNA from a single colony. This
196 sequence showed a 99% of identity with *Methylobacterium* spp. (*M. marchantiae* and
197 *M. bullatum*).

198 *Methylobacterium* species are considered Plant Growth Promoting Bacteria
199 (PGPB), so it was not entirely surprising that these bacteria might also interact with
200 *Chlamydomonas*, a green algal lineage ancestral to the land plants (Lewis and McCourt
201 2004). We explored the potential of *Chlamydomonas* to interact with *Methylobacterium*
202 spp. in relation to the use of amino acids and dipeptides. Specifically, we tested ten
203 different species of *Methylobacterium* covering the main branches of the
204 methylobacterial phylogeny (Figure 1; Dourado *et al.* 2015) in their ability to
205 complement *Chlamydomonas*’ lack of growth on dipeptides as a sole N-source. We
206 used the di-peptides L-Ala-Ala, Gly-Gly, L-Gly-Pro, L-Pro-Gly, L-Gly-Hyp, L-Hyp-
207 Gly, and the tripeptide L-Gly-Gly-Gly (Figure 1), along with the amino acids L-Pro and
208 L-Hyp, which have been shown not to be deaminated by CrLAO1 (Vallon *et al.* 1993).
209 These peptides were chosen in particular because they do not appear to support
210 metabolic activity in *Chlamydomonas* (Chaiboonchoe *et al.* 2014). *Chlamydomonas*
211 growth was not observed with any of these N-sources when grown alone (Figure 1A). In
212 contrast, co-culturing with different *Methylobacterium* species supported
213 *Chlamydomonas* growth with three major patterns observed (Figure 1B). First,
214 complementation specifically by *M. nodulans* and *M. aquaticum* allowed algal growth
215 on N-sources such as L-Pro and L-Pro-Gly. Second, all *Methylobacterium* species tested
216 led to algal growth in N-sources like the dipeptides L-Ala-Ala and Gly-Pro. Third, lack
217 of growth on L-Hyp could not be complemented by any of the *Methylobacterium*
218 species assayed (Figure 1B).

219

220 **A *Chlamydomonas*-*Methylobacterium* obligate mutualism underlying growth on L-**
221 **Pro**

222 Both closely-related *M. aquaticum* and *M. nodulans* were able to complement
223 *Chlamydomonas* growth (Figure 1). *M. nodulans* was able to grow alone in the presence
224 of L-Pro but has been reported to fix atmospheric N₂ (Jourand *et al.* 2004). In contrast,
225 *M. aquaticum*, which cannot fix N₂, showed defective growth on L-Pro (Figure 1A). We
226 found that co-culture with *Chlamydomonas* permitted both *M. aquaticum* and
227 *Chlamydomonas* to grow on L-Pro as a sole N-source in a mutually dependent fashion.
228 Using qPCR-based cell quantification, we did not detect cell growth in either algal or
229 bacterial monocultures, while growth was observed for both cells types in co-culture
230 (Figure 2A and B). When observed under the microscope, aggregates of *M. aquaticum*
231 were observed as previously reported (Gallego *et al.* 2005); in co-cultures,
232 *Chlamydomonas* cells appear to be embedded and attached to these bacterial aggregates
233 (Figure 2C and D). This physical association likely facilitates the exchange of
234 metabolites between both organisms.

235 *Chlamydomonas* can fix CO₂ under autotrophic conditions so N is expected to
236 generally be the limiting nutrient for algal growth. We hypothesized that *M. aquaticum*
237 might metabolize L-Pro and produce ammonium to sustain *Chlamydomonas* growth in
238 co-culture. We incubated *M. aquaticum* cells on L-Pro as sole N or C source for 48
239 hours and quantified ammonium in the supernatant and indeed found that ammonium
240 was produced by *M. aquaticum* and accumulated in the culture medium (Figure 3A).
241 We then asked whether *Chlamydomonas* might provide some reciprocal benefits,
242 specifically, a source of carbon that might be exuded during photosynthetic growth.
243 Glycerol plays key role in coral nutrition and growth during symbiosis with
244 dinoflagellates, and is the major end product of fixed CO₂ that these algae provide to the
245 coral host (Muscatine 1967; Suescún-Bolívar *et al.* 2012). Under stressful conditions
246 (e.g., osmotic stress), *Chlamydomonas* is known to produce glycerol and release it into
247 the media (Husic and Tolbert 1986; León and Galván 1994). Thus, we hypothesized that
248 *Chlamydomonas* might release glycerol under our culture conditions, and analyzed the
249 supernatants from *Chlamydomonas* cells incubated in L-Pro using HPLC. As shown in
250 Figure 3B, glycerol was detected in the media after 24h. In contrast, no glycerol
251 accumulated in the media in co-cultures, consistent with the fact that methylobacteria
252 can metabolize glycerol (Gallego *et al.* 2005).

253

1
2
3 254 Our data show that L-Pro was not used efficiently and that it may not be a
4 255 stoichiometrically balanced source of carbon and nitrogen for *M. aquaticum*. For
5 256 example, *M. aquaticum* growth on L-Pro led to a curious release of ammonium into the
6 257 media. We asked whether extra carbon input, in the form of glycerol, could balance the
7 258 carbon:nitrogen nutrient ratio leading to efficient *M. aquaticum* growth on L-Pro.
8 259 Indeed, glycerol promoted bacterial growth on L-Pro (Figure 3C) and also limited
9 260 ammonium excretion (Figure 3D).
10
11
12
13
14
15

261

262 **Methylobacterium genome analysis for L-Pro metabolism**

16
17 263 To understand the complementation patterns of different *Methylobacterium* co-cultured
18 264 with *Chlamydomonas*, we analyzed the (four) available *Methylobacterium* genome
19 265 sequences: *M. aquaticum* and *M. nodulans*, which complemented *Chlamydomonas*
20 266 growth on L-Pro and L-Pro-Gly, and *M. oryzae* and *M. extorquens*, which did not
21 267 (Figure 1). We focused on the set of putative genes involved in the L-Pro assimilation
22 268 and identified through reciprocal BLAST analysis with well-annotated genes from *E.*
23 269 *coli* and *Serratia marcescens* (Figure 4 and Supplemental Table S1). In bacteria, L-Pro
24 270 can be imported into the cell through different transport systems proP, proU and putP
25 271 (Culham *et al.* 1993). Putative genes coding for SSS transporters (Sodium Solute
26 272 Symporters) were present in all four genomes, but no *putP* orthologs were found. The
27 273 putative *proU* ABC transporter, was not found in all species but *M. oryzae*. The putative
28 274 *proP* Major Facilitator Superfamily (MFS) transporter was only found in *M. aquaticum*
29 275 (Figure 4).
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38

39 276 Once inside the cell, L-Pro is oxidized to glutamate in a two-step process carried
40 277 out by one single enzyme encoded by the gene *putA*. (Tanner 2008) (Figure 4).
41 278 Glutamate can be then oxidized by glutamate dehydrogenase generating ammonium and
42 279 α -ketoglutarate that feed into the central glutamine synthetase-glutamine oxoglutarate
43 280 aminotransferase (GS-GOGAT) cycle. The α -ketoglutarate also feeds into the
44 281 tricarboxylic acids cycle (TCA) for energy production. Putative orthologue for *putA* was
45 282 found in all four *Methylobacterium* species. Therefore, the presence of the L-Pro
46 283 transporter proP could explain *M. aquaticum* specific ability to complement
47 284 *Chlamydomonas* growth on L-Pro relative to the other *Methylobacterium* spp.
48 285 examined. The *M. aquaticum* genome also contains two genes coding for putative prolyl
49 286 | peptidases that support catabolism of dipeptides (e.g., prolyl-glycine). The evidences for
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

287 prolyl peptidase genes existing in the other *Methylobacterium* genomes, however, were
288 not conclusive.

289 From our gene inventory analysis, the metabolism of L-Pro by *M. aquaticum* is
290 expected to generate α -ketoglurate and ammonium. Since ammonium is released into
291 the medium, we speculate that α -ketoglutarate shunted to the TCA cycle may result in a
292 carbon:nitrogen imbalance vis-à-vis the GS-GOGAT cycle and ammonium assimilation.
293 Supplementation with glycerol carbon backbones, which also, feeds into the TCA cycle,
294 may restore balance and permit L-Proline-derived α -ketoglutarate to be directed towards
295 nitrogen assimilation instead.

297 **A carbon-nitrogen metabolic circuit between *Chlamydomonas* and** 298 ***Methylobacterium***

299 A carbon-for-nitrogen metabolic exchange circuit has been reported for
300 *Chlamydomonas* and fungi (Hom and Murray 2014). Under those culturing conditions,
301 the fungus metabolizes glucose to produce CO₂, which serves as a carbon source for the
302 alga, while the alga reduces NO₂ to NH₄⁺ as a source of N for the fungus. In the system
303 described here, the flow of carbon and nitrogen to and from *Chlamydomonas* is
304 reversed: *Methylobacterium* provides N (NH₄⁺) to *Chlamydomonas* (from L-Pro or
305 dipeptides), while *Chlamydomonas* provides carbon (glycerol) to the bacteria (Figure
306 5). This flow of carbon and nitrogen relative to the alga is also commonly observed in
307 lichens (Seneviratne and Indrasena 2006), the dinoflagellate-coral symbiosis
308 (Muscatine, 1967; Suescún-Bolívar *et al.* 2012) and bacteria-plants symbiosis (Vance *et*
309 *al.* 1998).

310 Although glycerol was the only form of carbon that we detected by HPLC under
311 our conditions (i.e. continuous light and aerobiosis), *Chlamydomonas* can also release
312 other small carbon compounds (Moroney *et al.* 1986; Mus *et al.* 2007) that could in
313 theory feed methylobacteria (Green 1992). For example, this alga can excrete formate,
314 acetate and ethanol in the dark (Mus *et al.* 2007). During normal light/dark cycles,
315 different carbon sources could be released by the alga, leading to different temporally-
316 phased nutrient exchanges with bacteria in natural contexts.

317 The aggregation of *Chlamydomonas* and methylobacteria (Figure 2D) raises the
318 question of whether this might be chemotactically-driven: are there molecular signals or
319 motifs that would attract *Methylobacterium* to *Chlamydomonas*? Plant-methylobacterial
320 interactions have been understood based on properties of the plant cell wall, which is

1
2
3 321 composed of a complex cellulose-xyloglucan network. During plant cell growth,
4 322 methyl-esterified pectins in the cell wall are de-methyl-esterified by pectin
5 323 methylesterases, which releases methanol and is a primary carbon source for
6 324 *Methylobacterium* spp. In contrast, the *Chlamydomonas* cell wall does not contain
7 325 cellulose but is composed of crystalline glycoproteins, predominantly hydroxyproline-
8 326 rich glycoproteins (Imam *et al.* 1985; Goodenough *et al.* 1986; Adair *et al.* 1987).
9 327 Similarly to plant cell walls, however, turnover of this cell wall framework takes place
10 328 during *Chlamydomonas* growth and proline- and hydroxyproline-rich polypeptide
11 329 fragments are released into the culture medium (Voigt, 1985, 1986). We hypothesize
12 330 that methylobacteria may take advantage of these peptide by-products of
13 331 *Chlamydomonas* cell growth, and that this serves as the incipient basis for mutualistic
14 332 carbon and nitrogen exchange.

15 333 Our newly described mutualism between *Chlamydomonas* and
16 334 *Methylobacterium* may be a useful model for understanding algal-bacterial interactions
17 335 for further synthetic ecology studies of biotechnological relevance (Hom *et al.* 2015).
18 336 Moreover, given the simplicity and experimental tractability, this new algal-
19 337 methylobacterial system may be a useful model for understanding the evolution of
20 338 plant-PGPB associations and elucidating plant-PGPB signalling.

21 339
22 340
23 341

24 342 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

25 343 This work was funded by MINECO (Grant BFU2015-70649-P), the European FEDER
26 344 program, Junta de Andalucía (BIO-502), the Plan Propio de la Universidad de Córdoba,
27 345 the U.E.INTERREG VA POCTEP-055_ALGARED_PLUS5_E, and by a travel grant
28 346 (*Beca de Movilidad Internacional de la Universidad de Córdoba*) to VC to pursue
29 347 aspects of this work in the lab of EH. We thank Michael Clear for designing the centrin
30 348 primers used in this study, and Hamilton Moore and Aitor Gómez for assistance with
31 349 experiments.

32 350
33 351
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

352 **REFERENCES**

- 353 Abanda-Nkpwatt D, Musch M, Tschiersch J *et al.* Molecular interaction between
354 *Methylobacterium extorquens* and seedlings: growth promotion, methanol
355 consumption, and localization of the methanol emission site. *J Exp Bot*
356 2006;**57**:4025–32.
- 357 Adair WS, Steinmetz SA, Mattson DM *et al.* Nucleated assembly of *Chlamydomonas*
358 and *Volvox* cell walls. *J Cell Biol* 1987;**105**:2373–82.
- 359 Chaiboonchoe A, Dohai BS, Cai H *et al.* Microalgal Metabolic Network Model
360 Refinement through High-Throughput Functional Metabolic Profiling. *Front*
361 *Bioeng Biotechnol* 2014;**2**:1–12.
- 362 Cho D-H, Ramanan R, Heo J *et al.* Enhancing microalgal biomass productivity by
363 engineering a microalgal–bacterial community. *Bioresour Technol* 2015;**175**:578–
364 85.
- 365 Culham DE, Lasby B, Marangoni AG *et al.* Isolation and Sequencing of *Escherichia*
366 *coli* Gene *proP* Reveals Unusual Structural Features of the Osmoregulatory
367 Proline/Betaine transporter, ProP. *J Mol Biol* 1993;**229**:268–76.
- 368 Dourado MN, Camargo Neves AA, Santos DS *et al.* Biotechnological and Agronomic
369 Potential of Endophytic Pink-Pigmented Methylophilic *Methylobacterium spp.*
370 *Biomed Res Int* 2015:1–19.
- 371 Fernández E, Galván A. Inorganic nitrogen assimilation in *Chlamydomonas*. *J Exp Bot*
372 2007;**58**:2279–87.
- 373 Gallego V, García MT, Ventosa A. *Methylobacterium hispanicum* sp. nov. and
374 *Methylobacterium aquaticum* sp. nov., isolated from drinking water. *Int J Syst Evol*
375 *Microbiol* 2005;**55**:281–7.
- 376 Goecke F, Thiel V, Wiese J *et al.* Algae as an important environment for bacteria –
377 phylogenetic relationships among new bacterial species isolated from algae.
378 *Phycologia* 2013;**52**:14–24.
- 379 Goodenough UW, Gebhart B, Mecham RE *et al.* Crystals of the *Chlamydomonas*
380 *reinhardtii* Cell Wall: Polymerization, Depolymerization, and Purification of
381 Glycoprotein Monomers. *J Cell Biol* 1986;**103**:405–17.
- 382 Gormant DS, Levine RP. Cytochrome *f* and Plastocyanin: Their Sequence in the
383 Photosynthetic Electron Transport Chain of *Chlamydomonas reinhardi*. *Proc Natl*
384 *Acad Sci USA* 1965;**54**:1665–9.

- 1
2
3 385 Green, PN. The genus *Methylobacterium*. In A. Balows, H. G. Trüper, M. Dworkin, W.
4 386 Harder & K.-H. Schleifer (2nd ed.) *The Prokaryotes*. New York: Springer, 1993 vol.
5 387 2:2342–2349.
6
7
8 388 Hirsch PR, Mauchline TH. The Importance of the Microbial N Cycle in Soil for Crop
9 389 Plant Nutrition. *Advances in Applied Microbiology* 2015;**93**:45–71.
10
11 390 Hom EFY, Murray AW. Niche Engineering Demonstrates a Latent Capacity for Fungal-
12 391 Algal Mutualism. *Science* 2015;**345**:94–8.
13
14 392 Hom EFY, Aiyar P, Schaeme D *et al.* A Chemical Perspective on Microalgal-Microbial
15 393 Interactions. *Trend Plant Sci* 2015; **11**:689-693.
16
17
18 394 Husic HD, Tolbert NE. Effect of Osmotic Stress on Carbon Metabolism in
19 395 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Plant Physiol* 1986;**82**:594–6.
20
21 396 Imam SH, Buchanan MJ, Shin HC *et al.* The *Chlamydomonas* cell wall:
22 397 characterization of the wall framework. *J Cell Biol* 1985;**101**:1599–607.
23
24 398 Jourand P, Giraud E, Béna G *et al.* *Methylobacterium nodulans* sp. nov., for a group of
25 399 aerobic, facultatively methylotrophic, legume root-nodule-forming and nitrogen-
26 400 fixing bacteria. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2004;**54**:2269–73.
27
28
29 401 Jurado-Oller JL, Dubini A, Galvan A, *et al.* Low oxygen levels contribute to improve
30 402 photohydrogen production in mixotrophic non-stressed *Chlamydomonas* cultures.
31 403 *Biotechnol Biofuels* 2015;**8**:149.
32
33 404 Kim BH, Ramanan R, Cho DH *et al.* Role of *Rhizobium*, a plant growth promoting
34 405 bacterium, in enhancing algal biomass through mutualistic interaction. *Biomass*
35 406 *and Bioenergy* 2014;**69**:95–105.
36
37
38 407 Kirk DL, Kirk MM. Carrier-mediated Uptake of Arginine and Urea by *Chlamydomonas*
39 408 *reinhardtii*. *Plant Physiol* 1978;**61**:556–60.
40
41
42 409 Koch FC, McMeekin TL. A new direct nesslerization micro-kjeldahl method and a
43 410 modification of the nessler-folin reagent for ammonia. *J. Am. Chem. Soc*
44 411 1924;**46**:2066-9
45
46
47 412 Kutschera U. Plant-Associated Methylobacteria as Co-Evolved Phytosymbionts. *Plant*
48 413 *Signal Behav Signal Behav* 2007;**2**:74–8.
49
50 414 León R, Galván F. Halotolerance studies on *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*: glycerol
51 415 excretion by free and immobilized cells. *J Appl Phycol* 1994;**6**:13–20.
52
53
54 416 Lewis LA, McCourt RM. Green algae and the origin of land plants. *Am J Bot*
55 417 2004;**91**:1535-1556.
56
57
58 418 Li X, Huang S, Yu J *et al.* Improvement of hydrogen production of *Chlamydomonas*
59
60

- 1
2
3 419 *reinhardtii* by co-cultivation with isolated bacteria. *Int J Hydrogen Energy*
4 420 2013;**38**:10779–87.
5
6 421 Madhaiyan M, Suresh RDV, Anandham *et al.* Plant growth-promoting
7 422 *Methylobacterium* induces defense responses in groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.)
8 423 compared with rot pathogens. *Curr Microbiol* 2006;**53**:270-6.
9
10 424 Mahdavi H, Prasad V, Liu Y *et al.* In situ biodegradation of naphthenic acids in oil
11 425 sands tailings pond water using indigenous algae–bacteria consortium. *Bioresour*
12 426 *Technol* 2015;**187**:97–105.
13
14 427 Mus F, Dubini A, Seibert M *et al.* Anaerobic Acclimation in *Chlamydomonas*
15 428 *reinhardtii*. *J Biol Chem* 2007;**282**:25475–86.
16
17 429 Muscatine L. Glycerol Excretion by Symbiotic Algae from Corals and *Tridacna* and Its
18 430 Control by the Host. *Science* 1967;**156**:516–9.
19
20 431 Moroney JV, Wilson BJ, Tolbert NE. Glycolate Metabolism and Excretion by
21 432 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Plant Physiol* 1986;**82**:821-826.
22
23 433 Pajares S, Bohannan BJM. Ecology of Nitrogen Fixing, Nitrifying, and Denitrifying
24 434 Microorganisms in Tropical Forest Soils. *Front Microbiol* 2016;**7**:1045.
25
26 435 Ramanan R, Kang Z, Kim BH *et al.* Phycosphere bacterial diversity in green algae
27 436 reveals an apparent similarity across habitats. *Algal Res* 2015a;**8**:140–4.
28
29 437 Ramanan R, Kim BH, Cho DH *et al.* Algae-bacteria interactions: Evolution, ecology
30 438 and emerging applications. *Biotechnol Adv* 2015b:1–16.
31
32 439 Rivas R, Velázquez E, Zurdo-Piñeiro JL *et al.* Identification of microorganisms by PCR
33 440 amplification and sequencing of a universal amplified ribosomal region present in
34 441 both prokaryotes and eukaryotes. *J Microbiol Methods* 2004;**56**:413–26.
35
36 442 Sambrook J, Frish EF, Maniatis T. *Molecular cloning: A Laboratory Manual* (2nd ed.)
37 443 New York: Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press, 1989.
38
39 444 Sanz-Luque E, Chamizo-Ampudia A, Llamas A *et al.* Understanding nitrate
40 445 assimilation and its regulation in microalgae. *Front Plant Sci* 2015;**6**:10817–85.
41
42 446 Seneviratne G, Indrasena IK. Nitrogen fixation in lichens is important for improved
43 447 rock weathering. *J Biosci* 2006;**31**:639–43.
44
45 448 Seymour JR, Amin SA, Raina JB *et al.* Zooming in the phycosphere: the ecological
46 449 interface for phytoplankton-bacteria relationships. *Nat Microbiol* 2017;**2**:17065
47
48 450 de Souza R, Ambrosini A, Passaglia LMP. Plant growth-promoting bacteria as
49 451 inoculants in agricultural soils. *Genet Mol Biol* 2015;**38**:401–19.
50
51 452 Suescún-Bolívar LP, Iglesias-Prieto R, Thomé PE. Induction of Glycerol Synthesis and
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 453 Release in Cultured *Symbiodinium*. *PLoS One* 2012;**7**:e47182.
- 4 454 Sy A, Giraud E, Jourand P *et al.* Methylo-trophic *Methylobacterium* Bacteria Nodulate
5 and Fix Nitrogen in Symbiosis with Legumes. *J Bacteriol* 2001;**183**:214–20.
6
- 7 455
8 456 Tanabe Y, Okazaki Y, Yoshida M *et al.* A novel alphaproteobacterial ectosymbiont
9 promotes the growth of the hydrocarbon-rich green alga *Botryococcus braunii*. *Sci*
10 *Rep* 2015;**5**:10467.
11
- 12 457
13 458
14 459 Tanner JJ. Structural biology of proline catabolism. *Amino Acids* 2008;**35**:719–30.
- 15 460 Vallon O, Bulté L, Kuras R *et al.* Extensive accumulation of an extracellular L-amino-
16 acid oxidase during gametogenesis of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Eur J Biochem*
17 1993;**215**:351–60.
18
- 19 461
20 462
21 463 Vance CP, Miller SS, Driscoll BT *et al.* Nodule Carbon Metabolism: Organic Acids for
22 N_2 Fixation. Springer, Dordrecht, 1998, 443–8.
- 23 464
24 465 Voigt J. Macromolecules released into the culture medium during the vegetative cell
25 cycle of the unicellular green alga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Biochem J*
26 1985;**226**:259–68.
27
- 28 466
29 467
30 468 Voigt J. Biosynthesis and Turnover of Cell Wall Glycoproteins during the Vegetative
31 Cell Cycle of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. 1986;**41**:885–96.
32
- 33 469
34 470 Wirth R, Lakatos G, Maróti G *et al.* Exploitation of algal-bacterial associations in a
35 two-stage biohydrogen and biogas generation process. *Biotechnol Biofuels*
36 2015;**8**:59.
37
- 38 471
39 472
40 473 Wu S, Li X, Yu J *et al.* Increased hydrogen production in co-culture of *Chlamydomonas*
41 *reinhardtii* and *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*. *Bioresour Technol* 2012;**123**:184–8.
42
- 43 474
44 475 Xie B, Bishop S, Stessman D *et al.* *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* thermal tolerance
45 enhancement mediated by a mutualistic interaction with vitamin B12-producing
46 bacteria. *ISME J* 2013;**7**:1544–55.
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Table 1. *Methylobacterium* spp used in this work.

Species name	Strain	ID	Isolated from	Source	Reference
<i>M. oryzae</i>	CBMB20	18207	Stem tissues of <i>Oryza sativa</i>	DSMZ	Madhaiyan et al. 2007
<i>Methylobacterium</i> sp.	88A	-	Lake Washington	Kindly provided by Prof. Ludmila Chistoserdova	-
<i>M. organophilum</i>	XX	ATCC 27886	Lake sediment	BCCM/LMG	Patt et al. 1976
<i>M. chlamydomonae</i>	M017	-	Solid culture of <i>Chlamydomonas</i> <i>reinhardtii</i>	This work	This work
<i>M. marchantiae</i>	JT1	21328	Thalus of <i>Marchantia</i> <i>polymorpha</i>	DSMZ	Schauer et al. 2011
<i>M. hispanicum</i>	GP34	16372	Drinking water	CECT	Gallego et al. 2005
<i>M. nodulans</i>	-	21967	Nodules of <i>Crotalaria</i> <i>podocarpa</i>	BCCM/LMG	Jourand et al. 2004
<i>M. aquaticum</i>	GR16T	16371	Drinking water	DSMZ	Gallego et al. 2005
<i>M. aerolatum</i>	5413S-11	19013	Air sample	DSMZ	Weon et al. 2008
<i>M. extorquens</i>	AM1	-	Airborne contaminant	Kindly provided by Prof. Cecilia Martinez-Gomez	Nunn and Lidstrom, 1986

DSMZ, German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures-Leibniz Institute; BCC/LMG, Belgian Coordinated Collections of Microorganisms; CECT, Spanish Type Culture Collection Collection-University of Valencia.

FIGURE LEGENDS**Figure 1.*****Chlamydomonas* growth complementation by different *Methylobacterium* species.**

Maximum likelihood tree was performed using 16S rDNA sequences. *Chlamydomonas* and *Methylobacterium* species were grown on monocultures (A) and cocultures (B) on 8 mM of the indicated L-amino acids or peptides as the sole added N and C source. -N, without any N source; P: L-Proline; H, 4-hydroxy-L-proline; A₂: L-Ala-Ala; G₂, Gly-Gly; G₃, Gly-Gly-Gly; GP, Gly-Pro; PG, L-Pro-Gly; GH, Gly-Hyp; HP, L-Hyp-Gly. *Mory*, *M. oryzae*; *M88A*, *Methylobacterium* sp. 88^a; *Morg*, *M. organophilum*; *Mchl*, *Methylobacterium* sp. isolated in this work (M017); *Mmar*, *M. marchantiae*; *Mhis*, *M. hispanicum*; *Mnod*, *M. nodulans*; *Maqu*, *M. aquaticum*; *Maer*, *M. aerolatum*; *Mext*, *M. extorquens*. Liquid cultures on V-bottom 96 wells plates were centrifuged to pellet the cells prior to imaging, after 8 days for amino acids and 12 days for peptides. Green spots correspond to pelleted algal growth.

Figure 2.***Chlamydomonas* and *Methylobacterium aquaticum* growth on L-Proline. A,**

Chlamydomonas and *M. aquaticum* monocultures and cocultures growth on L-Pro after 11 days. The initial optical density was A₆₀₀ 0.002 for the bacteria and A₇₅₀ 0.025 for the alga. **B**, Cell quantification by qPCR from cultures in A. **C**, Optical microscopy image of *Chlamydomonas*-*M. aquaticum* coculture in A. 40x magnification (**C**), and zoomed image (**D**) corresponding to the black framed area. Color-less aggregates correspond to bacterial cells (Ma) and rounded green cells stuck to the aggregates correspond to algal cells (Cr).

Figure 3.**Ammonium and glycerol exchange between *Chlamydomonas* and *M. aquaticum*. A,**

Ammonium was determined in the supernatant of axenically grown *M. aquaticum* after 48 hours on 8 mM L-Pro, and without any added N (-N). Control without cells to account for any ammonium generated by spontaneous L-Pro degradation (- cells control). **B**, Glycerol quantification from *Chlamydomonas* and *Chlamydomonas*-*M. aquaticum* cultures supernatants on L-Pro. **C**, Effect of glycerol (8 mM)

1
2
3 supplementation to *M. aquaticum* growth on L-Pro (8 mM). Initial cell density was A_{600}
4 0.01. **D**, Ammonium quantification from the cultures in C.
5
6
7

8 **Figure 4.**

9 **Putative L-Proline utilization pathways by *Methylobacterium* species.** Putative
10 genes coding for each enzyme are listed in white. *proU*, glycine betaine/proline ABC
11 transporter; *proP*, proline permease (MFS transporter); *putA*, bifunctional proline
12 dehydrogenase; Pyr5C, Δ^1 -pyrroline-5-carboxylate; *GDH*, glutamate dehydrogenase;
13 *GS*, glutamine synthetase; *GOGAT*, glutamine oxoglutarate aminotransferase; TCA,
14 tricarboxylic acids. Colored dots correspond to orthologous genes found on each
15 indicated *Methylobacterium* spp. genome by a reciprocal BLAST hit approach.
16
17
18
19
20
21
22

23 **Figure 5.**

24 **Hypothesized carbon-nitrogen metabolic exchange circuit between**
25 ***Chlamydomonas* and *Methylobacterium* spp.**

26 *Chlamydomonas* may provide *Methylobacterium* spp organic carbon sources that are
27 byproducts of photosynthesis (e.g. glycerol). The cell wall composition of the alga, rich
28 in glycoproteins containing glycine, proline and hydroxiproline, may serve to attract
29 associations with *Methylobacterium* spp. In turn, *Methylobacterium* spp can transform
30 the Gly, Pro, Hyp containing peptides (which *Chlamydomonas* can not use) into a
31 bioavailable N (e.g. ammonium). This carbon-nitrogen metabolic exchange could
32 establish a mutualistic interaction between *Chlamydomonas* and *Methylobacterium* spp.
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Figure 1. *Chlamydomonas* growth complementation by different *Methylobacterium* species.

Maximum likelihood tree was performed using 16S rDNA sequences. *Chlamydomonas* and *Methylobacterium* species were grown on monocultures (**A**) and cocultures (**B**) on 8 mM of the indicated L-amino acids or peptides as the sole added N and C source. -N, without any N source; P: L-Proline; H, 4-hydroxy-L-proline; A₂: L-Ala-Ala; G₂, Gly-Gly; G₃, Gly-Gly-Gly; GP, Gly-Pro; PG, L-Pro-Gly; GH, Gly-Hyp; HP, L-Hyp-Gly. *Mory*, *M. oryzae*; *M88A*, *Methylobacterium sp. 88^a*; *Morg*, *M. organophilum*; *Mchl*, *Methylobacterium sp. isolated in this work (M017)*; *Mmar*, *M. marchantiae*; *Mhis*, *M. hispanicum*; *Mnod*, *M. nodulans*; *Maqu*, *M. aquaticum*; *Maer*, *M. aerolatum*; *Mext*, *M. extorquens*. Liquid cultures on V-bottom 96 wells plates were centrifuged to pellet the cells prior to imaging, after 8 days for amino acids and 12 days for peptides. Green spots correspond to pelleted algal growth.

319x184mm (300 x 300 DPI)

27 **Figure 2. *Chlamydomonas* and *Methylobacterium aquaticum* growth on L-Proline. A,**
28 *Chlamydomonas* and *M. aquaticum* monocultures and cocultures growth on L-Pro after 11 days. The initial
29 optical density was A600 0.002 for the bacteria and A750 0.025 for the alga. **B,** Cell quantification by qPCR
30 from cultures in A. **C,** Optical microscopy image of *Chlamydomonas-M. aquaticum* coculture in A. 40x
31 magnification (**C**), and zoomed image (**D**) corresponding to the black framed area. Color-less aggregates
32 correspond to bacterial cells (Ma) and rounded green cells stuck to the aggregates correspond to algal cells
(Cr).

33 240x136mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 3. Ammonium and glycerol exchange between *Chlamydomonas* and *M. aquaticum*. **A**, Ammonium was determined in the supernatant of axenically grown *M. aquaticum* after 48 hours on 8 mM L-Pro, and without any added N (-N). Control without cells to account for any ammonium generated by spontaneous L-Pro degradation (- cells control). **B**, Glycerol quantification from *Chlamydomonas* and *Chlamydomonas-M. aquaticum* cultures supernatants on L-Pro. **C**, Effect of glycerol (8 mM) supplementation to *M. aquaticum* growth on L-Pro (8 mM). Initial cell density was A_{600} 0.01. **D**, Ammonium quantification from the cultures in C.

159x149mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 4. Putative L-Proline utilization pathways by Methylobacterium species. Putative genes coding for each enzyme are listed in white. *proU*, glycine betaine/proline ABC transporter; *proP*, proline permease (MFS transporter); *putA*, bifunctional proline dehydrogenase; Pyr5C, Δ^1 -pyrroline-5-carboxylate; **GDH**, glutamate dehydrogenase; **GS**, glutamine synthetase; **GOGAT**, glutamine oxoglutarate aminotransferase; TCA, tricarboxylic acids. Colored dots correspond to orthologous genes found on each indicated *Methylobacterium spp.* genome by a reciprocal BLAST hit approach.

240x130mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 5. Hypothesized carbon-nitrogen metabolic exchange circuit between *Chlamydomonas* and *Methylobacterium spp.*!! † *Chlamydomonas* may provide *Methylobacterium spp.* organic carbon sources that are byproducts of photosynthesis (e.g. glycerol). The cell wall composition of the alga, rich in glycoproteins containing glycine, proline and hydroxiprolin, may serve to attract associations with *Methylobacterium spp.* In turn, *Methylobacterium spp.* can transform the Gly, Pro, Hyp containing peptides (which *Chlamydomonas* can not use) into a bioavailable N (e.g. ammonium). This carbon-nitrogen metabolic exchange could establish a mutualistic interaction between *Chlamydomonas* and *Methylobacterium spp.*!! †

240x155mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Supplemental Table S1. Best hits for putative orthologous genes involved in L-Proline import and assimilation in *Methylobacterium* species found by reciprocal Blast hit approach.

Function	Protein	Activity	Query Protein	<i>M. aquaticum</i>	<i>M. nodulans</i>	<i>M. oryzae</i>	<i>M. extorquens</i>
Uptake	Proline/Na ⁺ symporter (SSS)	putP	P07117	-			
	Proline permease, MFS	proP	P0C0L7	Maq22A_c0108 5			
	ProU ABS transporter, ATP-binding protein	proV	P14175	Maq22A_c1568 5 Maq22A_1p332 75	Mnod_840 1		Mex_1p4103
	ProU ABS transporter, membrane protein	proW	P14176	Maq22A_c1568 0 Maq22A_1p332 70	Mnod_340 7 Mnod_840 2	-	Mex_1p4104
	ProU ABS transporter, periplasmic protein	proX	P0AFM2	Maq22A_c1567 5	Mnod_340 6		Mex_1p4105
	Assimilation	Proline dehydrogenase/Pyr5C dehydrogenase	putA GD	P09546	Maq22A_c2068 0	Mnod_144 1	MOC_343 2
Glutamate dehydrogenase		H	P00370	Maq22A_c2454 0	Mnod_452 1	MOC_007 7	-
Peptidase	Proline iminopeptidase	Pip	O32449	Maq22A_c2508 0			
				Maq22A_c2753 5			